

ELECTROCHEMICAL TREATMENT OF TURBID RAW WATER FROM OPA DAM, OBAFEMI AWOLOWO UNIVERSITY, ILE-IFE, NIGERIA

¹Abah, U. J., ^{1*}Oke, I.A.; ²Akanni A. O.; ³Williams-Bello, U.P.; ¹Aladekomo, J.O., ⁴Olayanju, O.K.

¹ Department of Civil Engineering, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Nigeria

²Civil Engineering Department, Federal Polytechnic, Ile- Oluji, Nigeria

³Federal Ministry of Works and Housing Highway Construction and Rehabilitation Department, Abuja Nigeria

⁴ Department of Civil Engineering, Redeemer's University, Ede, Nigeria

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*okeia@oauife.edu.ng

ABSTRACT

Water scarcity affects over 2 billion people globally, with the United Nations predicting that by 2025, half the world's population will live in water-stressed areas. Contaminated sources of water with pollutants such as heavy metals like lead, cadmium, and copper pose severe health risks. Traditional water treatment approaches often fail to remove these pollutants, highlighting the need for advanced treatment techniques such as electrochemical treatment. This study evaluated the performance of electrochemical treatment (Al-Al electrodes) in removing selected pollutants from turbid raw water obtained from Opa dam, located at Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Nigeria. Effects of selected factors (volume of water to electrolyte ratio, treatment duration, electrode spacing and applied current) were evaluated and optimized using the Taguchi technique. The results revealed that the electrochemical treatment significantly reduced the concentrations of all targeted contaminants. The highest removal efficiencies achieved were 58.35 % for turbidity, 88.10 % for total dissolve solids, 92.31 % for chloride, 31.18 % for copper, 90.21 % for zinc, 56.33 % for lead, and 57.71 % for cadmium. Optimal treatment conditions varied for each parameter. The optimal conditions were a volume ratio of 1.75, a treatment time of 35 minutes, electrode spacing of 1.2 cm, and a current of 1.5 A for turbidity removal. In conclusion, the study established the effectiveness of electrochemical treatment in removing selected pollutants from turbid raw water. The optimum values of the system varied with the parameters and the factors. The study provided a framework for enhancing water treatment processes using electrochemical methods and thereby contributes to sustainable development Goal 6.

Keywords: Water scarcity, Electrochemical treatment, Water-stressed, Taguchi technique, Advanced treatment techniques, Health risks

INTRODUCTION

Water scarcity affects over 2 billion people globally, with the United Nations predicting that by 2025, half the world's population will live in water-stressed areas (UN Water, 2018; WHO, 2021). It is well established that sources of typical water (ground and surface) are facing critical deterioration in qualities due to various activities of man such as industrialization, agricultural practices, urbanization, and the relentless expansion of population (Mojiri *et al.*, 2024; Zhou *et al.*, 2024). Contaminated sources of water with pollutants such as heavy metals like lead, cadmium, and copper pose severe health risks (Nazmuz 2012; Topal *et al.*, 2024; Wang *et al.*, 2022). Traditional treatment approaches often fail to remove these pollutants, highlighting the need for advanced treatment techniques such as electrochemical treatment (Gomez *et al.*, 2018; Daneshva *et al.*, 2020; Hong *et al.*, 2020; Mishra *et al.*, 2021). Electrochemical treatment techniques are electrical and voltage-driven technologies that have been utilised successfully in saline water and brine desalination

(Fehintola *et al.*, 2024; Amoko *et al.*, 2024; Kaya, 2024). The treatment technique is based on the selective transportation of ions in aqueous solutions or electrolyte and utilises an applied electrical voltage gradient, difference, or slope to drive anions and cations in opposite directions to the electrode (Nabgan *et al.*, 2022; Khorram *et al.*, 2023). Although, advanced oxidation processes are also highly effective for degrading recalcitrant organic pollutants in water and wastewater treatment, electrochemical treatment techniques processes are adaptable and can be tailored to various types of water and wastewater, addressing specific treatment needs to meet regulatory requirements (Islam, 2019; Hong *et al.*, 2020; Görmez and Gizir, 2024). Electrochemical treatment techniques often complement traditional treatment methods, enhancing overall system performance. The electrochemical treatment techniques is relatively inexpensive due to its lower equipment and maintenance costs and because no additional chemicals are required (Daneshvar *et al.*, 2020; Obijole, *et al.*, 2022a and b; Asaithambi *et al.*, 2024).The category and treatment of water and wastewater using electrochemical treatment

techniques are controlled by several factors, which include nature, and size of reactive species to be generated in electrochemical treatment techniques processes the type of the treatment technique, electrode or electro catalyst materials, water or wastewater composition, water or wastewater pH settings, and operational constraints (Koby and Gengec, 2012; Drouiche *et al.*, 2009; Bensadok *et al.*, 2008; Trung *et al.*, 1982; Ahlawat *et al.*, 2008; Tchamango *et al.*, 2010; Mameri *et al.*, 2001; Espinoza-Quiñones *et al.*, 2009; Petric *et al.*, 2013; Koby *et al.*, 2018; Pothanamkandathil *et al.*, 2020; Sun *et al.*, 2021). Electrochemical treatment techniques can be in form of any of these treatment techniques: electrooxidation, electro-sorption, electrocoagulation, electro flo to coagulation, electro-Fenton process, son electro catalysis, electro-deionization, electrochemical membrane or electro-filtration processes, photoelectrochemical treatment, electrochemical disinfection, electrochemical peroxidation, electrochemical desalination or capacitive deionization, electrochemical reduction, electrochemical advanced oxidation, and electrodialysis (Oke *et al.*, 2020; Mishra *et al.*, 2021; Fehintola *et al.*, 2024; Amoko *et al.*, 2024). Figure 1a presents publications on electrochemical treatment techniques in selected countries between 1977 and 2022 while Figure 1b presents the classifications

With reference to the urgent needs for sustainable development goals, based on the relationship between economy, environment, society, poverty eradication (Dalampira and Nastis, 2019), and sustainable water and wastewater management, there is a critical need to further evaluate the efficacy of electrochemical treatment techniques in reducing selected pollutants from turbid raw water, which is a common surface water in Osun State, Nigeria. The main objectives of the current study are to examine the source and the causes of turbid raw water in Opa river, evaluate the efficacy of electrochemical treatment techniques process (utilising aluminium-aluminium electrodes) in removing selected pollutants such as turbidity, total dissolve solids (TDS), chloride, zinc, lead and cadmium from turbid raw water, examine effects of selected operational factors (volume of water to electrolyte ratio, treatment duration, electrode spacing and applied current) and optimise selected operational factors using the Taguchi technique.

METHODOLOGY

The materials and method used in the study can be summarized as follows:

Collection turbid raw water samples

The sampling method used in this study was the purposive sampling technique. Turbid raw water samples were collected monthly from Opa dam at three different times in the following locations as follows; point A (Latitude 07.50267° N and Longitude 004.52966° E, Figure 3a), point B (Latitude 07.50300° N and Longitude 004.52928° E, Figure 3b) and point C (Latitude 07.50308° N and Longitude 004.522917° E, Figure 3c) between June and October 2023.

Water treatment and experimental setup for the electrochemical treatment

The collected turbid raw water samples were subjected to electrochemical treatment techniques utilising aluminium (anode) and aluminium (cathode) electrodes in a reactor (Figure 4). The choice of electro-coagulation and electro-oxidation was based on the two electrodes selected, which was based on impacts and effectiveness of the electrodes, water treatment systems, influence on operational costs, treatment efficiency, and system durability (Koby and Gengec, 2012; Drouiche *et al.*, 2009; Bensadok *et al.*, 2008; Trung *et al.*, 1982; Ahlawat *et al.*, 2008; Tchamango *et al.*, 2010; Mameri *et al.*, 2001; Espinoza-Quiñones *et al.*, 2009; Petric *et al.*, 2013; Fehintola *et al.*, 2024)

Analysis of concentration of the pollutants and performance computation:

All chemicals and reagents used in this study had a chemical purity of 95% or above. Distilled water was used in the preparations of primary and secondary standard solutions. All equipment used in the experiments were calibrated and the coefficient of determinations of these calibrations (relationship between expected and obtained values) were 96 % or above. Concentrations of the pollutants in both turbid raw and treated water were conducted utilising the method and procedures specified in the Standard Methods for Water and Wastewater Examination such as APHA (2012) and Van Loosdrecht *et al.* (2016). The choice of the standard methods was based on accuracy, type of water and availability of required reagents. Pollutant's concentration was calculated using equation (1) as follows:

$$X(\text{mg} / \text{l}) = \left(\frac{(A - B) N_0 P_1}{V_s} \right) C_f \quad (1)$$

Where; N_0 stands for normality of reagent used, P_1 stands for dilution factor; V_s stands for volume of sample used (ml), A stands for volume of the titrate used or reading for the sample (ml), C_f stands for calibration factor and B stands for volume of the titrate used or reading for the blank (ml). Individual efficiencies of the process were based mainly on pollutant removal (Table 1, Y , %), which was computed using equation (2).

$$Y(\%) = 100 \left(\frac{(C_0 - C_t)}{C_0} \right) \quad (2)$$

Where: C_0 stands for initial pollutant's concentration of the raw water (mg/l). C_t stands for final pollutant's concentration in the treated water (mg/l) and Y stands for pollutant removed (%).

Effects and optimization of selected factors on the performance of electrochemical treatment

The influence of selected factors (volume of water to electrolyte ratio, treatment duration, electrode spacing and applied current) on the efficacy of the electrochemical treatment process were monitored utilising fractional factorial experiment (Table 1) and optimised utilising

Taguchi technique. The choice of these factors to be studied was based on the theoretical data on several factors that determine the performance of an electrochemical treatment process and the knowledge concerning aluminium and aluminium electrodes (Kobyta and Gengec, 2012; Drouiche

Where; G_{si} is the sum of the performance of factor “s” and level “i”; R_{si} is the performance of factor “s” and level “i” and X_{avsi} is the average performance of factor “s” and level “i”. Effects of operational factors that can influence performance of the system were evaluated using $L_{16} 4^4$

Figure 1: Publications on Electrochemical Treatment Technique from selected countries between 1977 and 2022 (Source: Mao et al., 2023)

Figure 1b: Classification of Electrochemical Treatment Processes (Source: Mao et al., 2023)

et al., 2009; Bensadok et al., 2008; Trung et al., 1982; Ahlawat et al., 2008; Tchamango et al., 2010; Mameri et al., 2001; Espinoza-Quñones et al., 2009; Petric et al., 2013).

Statistical computation of parameters

The choice of this statistical measure as the quality characteristic is analysed based on the need to control both

orthogonal array (Table 1). The effects were analysed using analysis of variance (ANOVA). The total sum of squared deviations (SST) is calculated from the total average of the operational factors as per the following equation (Shi et al., 2023; Idi et al., 2024):

Figure 2: An Overview of the Distribution and Transportation of the Pollutants (PFAS) in the Natural Environment (Source: Liu et al., 2023)

the mean level of the process, and the variation around this mean. All statistical analysis (analysis of variance and optimise selected operational factors) were conducted according to Oke (2009) and Fehintola et al. (2024).

Computation of Average of the level: The sum and average of various levels of the selected factors were computed using equations (3 to 9) as follows (Shi et al., 2023; Idi et al., 2024):

$$G_{si} = \sum_{i=1}^4 R_{si} \quad (3)$$

$$X_{avsi} = 0.25 \times G_{si} \quad (4)$$

$$SST = \sum_{i=1}^N (X_i - \bar{X}_T)^2 \quad (5)$$

Where, X_i is the performance of experiment i; SST is the total sum of squared deviations of performance; N is the number of experiments and \bar{X}_T is the overall average of the performance. This total sum of squared deviation, SST, occurs due to the sum of squared deviations due to each control factor (SS_A, SS_B, SS_C, SS_D and SS_E) and the sum of squared deviations due to error, (SS_e). The sum of squared deviation due to the factor is calculated as by (Shi et al., 2023; Idi et al., 2024):

Figure 3a: Sampling Point A (Source: Google Earth Pro, 2024)

Figure 3a: Sampling Point A (Source: Google Earth Pro, 2024)

Figure 3c: Sampling Point C (Source: Google Earth Pro, 2024)

Table 1: Design matrix and the experimental results for the L16 (44) orthogonal array

Experiment	Factors and their studying levels				Y (%)
	Vol(A) ml	Time (B)min	Space(cm)	Current (A)	
1	1	1	1	1	1
2	1	2	2	2	2
3	1	3	3	3	3
4	1	4	4	4	4
5	2	1	2	3	3
6	2	2	1	4	4
7	2	3	4	1	1
8	2	4	3	2	2
9	3	1	3	4	4
10	3	2	4	3	3
11	3	3	1	2	2
12	3	4	2	1	1
13	4	1	4	2	2
14	4	2	3	1	1
15	4	3	2	4	4
16	4	4	1	3	3

$$SSF_i = \frac{1}{N_j} \sum_{j=1}^{N_j} (\bar{X}_j - \bar{X}_T)^2 \quad (6)$$

Where: F_i is the factor i (A, B, C, D-----N) \bar{X}_j is the average of the response of the factor F_i at level j and j is the level of the factor F_i (1, 2, ----- N_j). The sum of squared deviation due to the error (SS_e) and degree of freedoms are calculated as by (Shi *et al.*, 2023; Idi *et al.*, 2024):

$$SS_e = SST - SSA - SSB - SSC - \dots - SSN \quad (7)$$

$$d_{Tfe} = N - 1 \quad (8)$$

$$d_{Fje} = N_j - 1 \quad (9)$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results from this study are presented as follows:

The source, the causes and characteristics of turbid raw water:

The study revealed that the turbid water was caused by the mining activities (wet process of mining) within the

Figure 4: Laboratory Setup of the System (Electrochemical Treatment of Al-Al electrodes)

Figure 5a: Aerial View of all the Sites (Source: Google Earth Pro, 2024)

Figure 5b: Clear view of Selected First Portion (Source: Google Earth Pro, 2024)

Figure 5c: Clear view of Selected Second Portion (Source: Google Earth Pro, 2024)

catchment of the dam. Figure 5 presents the aerial view of the mining site within the catchment. The figure revealed that there were over sixty (60) ponds (smaller, medium and

large) within the catchment. The ponds consist of mud and swamp stagnant dirty water that overflow into the river (river opa), which is the major source of water for opa dam.

Table 2 presents the average compositions of selected water quality parameters. The Table revealed that the average turbidity of the water samples was 688.00 NTU and chloride concentration was 12.00 mg/l, Zinc, Copper, Lead and Cadmium concentrations (mg/l) at Opa dam were 17.05, 0.42, 0.59 and 0.56, respectively. Although, these

Jin *et al.*, (2024); Wang *et al.*, (2023); Mao *et al.*, (2021); Mulyono *et al.*, (2022); Liang *et al.*, (2021); Ghosh *et al.*, (2023) and Zhang *et al.*, (2023) on performance of electrochemical treatment of water using Al- Al electrodes. **Skewness** is a quantity of the asymmetry of a distribution of selected data. A distribution is asymmetrical if its right and

Table 2: Characteristics of the Raw Water Samples

	Point A	Point B	Point C	Average	Standard deviation	Variance
Turbidity(NTU)	689.00	687.00	688.00	688.00	0.82	0.67
TDS (mg/L)	42.00	38.00	40.00	40.00	1.63	2.67
Chloride(mg/L)	13.00	11.00	12.00	12.00	0.82	0.67
Zinc (mg/L)	16.90	16.70	17.05	16.88	0.14	0.02
Copper (mg/L)	0.20	0.21	0.42	0.27	0.10	0.01
Lead (mg/L)	0.56	0.56	0.59	0.57	0.01	0.00
Cadmium (mg/L)	0.57	0.57	0.56	0.57	0.01	0.00

Figure 6: Schematic Diagrams of Pollutants Removal by (a) Electro-oxidation, (b) Electro-adsorption and (c) Electro-coagulation (Source: Liu *et al.*, 2023)

concentrations were lower than concentration obtained at the upstream of the dam at Road 7 bridge (another study), the characteristics are similar to wastewater from mining sites of high lead and cadmium concentrations (Palomo-Briones *et al.*, 2016a and b; Andrade *et al.*, 2017; Acheampong, 2013; Benavente *et al.*, 2011; Acheampong *et al.*, 2010; Acheampong *et al.*, 2013a and b). These results show that there are some preliminary treatments such as sedimentation processes, aeration and self-purification along the river.

Evaluate the efficacy of electrochemical treatment techniques process

Table 3 shows the efficacies of the system in removing or reducing selected pollutants. The Table revealed that the performance average, standard deviation and skewness of the parameters (turbidity, TDS, chloride, zinc, lead and cadmium) were 43.934 %, 1.654 and 2.248; 68.703 %, 7.475, and -0.609; 68.389 %, 12.925 and 0.111; 51.049 %, 21.010 and 0.152; 21.797 %, 3.097 and -0.099 ; 34.407 %, 12.656 and -0.047; and 29.460 %, 13.892, and -0.170. These results of the performance revealed that the system can remove selected pollutants from turbid raw water. The performance agreed with literature such as He *et al.*, (2020 and 2023); Yu *et al.*, (2022); Zhou *et al.*, (2022); Huangfu *et al.*, (2023); Tian *et al.*, (2022); Liu *et al.*, (2023 and 2024);

left sides are not mirror images. A distribution or skewness can have right (or positive, greater than zero), left (or negative skewness when less than zero), or zero skewness. A right-skewed distribution is longer on the right side of its peak, and a left-skewed distribution is longer on the left side of its peak. The results of the performance established a mixed skewness for the performance in respect of the parameters. The mechanism and chemistry of the system revealed that the electrochemical reaction that occurred at the anode and involved metal M-aluminium in the present case, which can be written as follows (Drouiche *et al.*, 2009; Tchamango *et al.*, 2010; Mi *et al.*, 2012; Nabgan *et al.*, 2022):

Hydrogen evolution occurs at the cathode depending on pH.

The generated Al^{3+} ions combine with water and hydroxyl ions to form corresponding hydroxides and polyhydroxides as follows (Bensadok *et al.*, 2008; Kobya and Gengec, 2012; Paulista *et al.*, 2018):

a) monomeric species such as $Al(OH)^{2+}$, $Al(OH)^{2+}$, and $Al(OH)^{4+}$

b) polymeric species such as $Al_2(OH)_2^{4+}$ and $Al_2(OH)^{5+}$,

c) amorphous and less soluble species such as $Al(OH)_3$ and Al_2O_3 .

Figure 6 presents schematic diagrams of pollutants removal by (a) electro-oxidation, (b) electro-adsorption and (c) electro-coagulation.

Optimise Selected Operational Factors

Figures 6, 7 and 8 show the results of the optimization using Taguchi technique. The figures revealed optimum values of the system varied with the parameters and the factors. Figures 6a and 6b are for optimum values for the factor in respect to the turbidity. These figures and graphs A, B, C and D affirmed that the optimum value for the selected factors (volume of water to electrolyte ratio, treatment duration, electrode spacing and applied current) are 1.70, 37 minutes, 1.25 cm and 1.75 A, respectively. Figures 7a and 6b are for optimum values for the factor in respect to lead concentration. These figures and graphs A, B, C and D affirmed that the optimum value for the selected factors (volume of water to electrolyte ratio, treatment duration, electrode spacing and applied current) are 1.83, 33 minutes,

Table 3: The Summary of the Performance of the System

Experiment Number	Code	Turbidity Average	TDS Average	Chloride Average	Zinc Average	Copper Average	Lead Average	Cadmium Average
1	1111	43.90	76.30	66.73	71.56	19.53	15.45	7.63
2	1222	43.70	64.74	94.41	67.91	22.66	19.95	5.17
3	1333	43.31	72.54	69.58	51.49	20.88	45.64	19.10
4	1444	43.85	58.35	52.59	56.85	24.22	28.35	31.99
5	2123	43.56	67.36	67.02	76.32	23.26	41.99	17.53
6	2214	43.80	68.95	86.07	42.43	16.66	17.78	43.32
7	2341	42.73	68.91	66.22	20.40	21.44	28.70	32.41
8	2432	42.63	76.00	42.33	27.25	20.80	41.73	16.84
9	3133	43.17	74.38	83.26	71.42	22.15	22.03	28.33
10	3244	43.12	71.49	61.13	65.53	25.53	51.49	37.65
11	3311	43.56	80.85	75.78	44.44	24.80	40.74	28.19
12	3422	43.41	75.04	58.82	34.00	22.20	45.83	22.38
13	4141	43.22	66.74	74.42	22.25	20.47	52.53	40.35
14	4232	47.91	61.89	65.75	43.14	15.77	26.72	53.02
15	4323	48.20	51.76	71.82	32.45	20.40	24.74	41.35
16	4414	42.88	63.94	58.31	89.35	27.99	46.84	46.11
Mean		43.934	68.703	68.389	51.049	21.797	34.407	29.460
SD		1.654	7.475	12.925	21.010	3.097	12.656	13.892
Skewness		2.248	-0.609	0.111	0.152	-0.099	-0.047	-0.170

Table 4a: ANOVA for Turbidity

Factor	Sum of Square	Degree of freedom	Mean Sum of Square	F-Value
A	14.52	3	4.84	34.13
B	6.11	3	2.04	14.35
C	5.49	3	1.83	12.89
D	7.70	3	2.57	18.09
SS error	7.23	51	0.14	
SS total	41.05	63	0.65	

Table 4b: ANOVA for TDS

Factor	Sum of Square	Degree of freedom	Mean Sum of Square	F-Value
A	426.18	3	142.06	240.23
B	40.52	3	13.51	22.84
C	167.99	3	56.00	94.69
D	173.37	3	57.79	97.72
SS error	30.16	51	0.59	
SS total	838.21	63	13.30	

Effects of selected operational factors

Table 4 shows results of ANOVA for all the parameters. These tables revealed that the selected factors are significant in the removal of the pollutants ($F_{3,3} = 5.39$ at 10 % confidence level and 9.28 at 5 % confidence level) expect Table 4c where $F_{3,3} = 2.14$ for factor A (volume of water to electrolyte ratio) for chloride removal, indicating the factor is not significant in the removal of chloride from turbid water.

1.25 cm and 1.75 A, respectively. Figures 8a and 8b are for optimum values for the factor in respect to cadmium concentration. These figures and graphs A, B, C and D affirmed that the optimum value for the selected factors (volume of water to electrolyte ratio, treatment duration, electrode spacing and applied current) are 1.83, 36 minutes, 1.25 cm and 1.18 A, respectively. These results agreed with previous studies such as Kobya and Gengec (2012); Drouiche *et al.* (2009); Bensadok *et al.* (2008); Trung *et al.* (1982); Ahlawat *et al.* (2008); Tchamango *et al.* (2010); Mameri *et al.* (2001); Espinoza-Quñones *et al.* (2009); Petric *et al.* (2013) and Fehintola *et al.* (2024).

Table 4c: ANOVA for Chloride

Factor	Sum of Square	Degree of freedom	Mean Sum of Square	F-Value
A	69.32	3.00	23.11	2.14
B	1,335.52	3.00	445.17	41.19
C	262.18	3.00	87.39	8.09
D	287.62	3.00	95.87	8.87
SS error	551.23	51.00	10.81	1.00
SS total	2,505.87	63.00	39.78	3.68

Table 4d: ANOVA for Copper

Factor	Sum of Square	Degree of freedom	Mean Sum of Square	F-Value
A	21.98	3	7.33	14.93
B	27.68	3	9.23	18.80
C	20.62	3	6.87	14.01
D	48.57	3	16.19	32.99
SS error	25.03	51	0.49	
SS total	143.87	63	2.28	

Table 4e: ANOVA for Lead

Factor	Sum of Square	Degree of freedom	Mean Sum of Square	F-Value
A	382.85	3	127.62	25.89
B	284.49	3	94.83	19.24
C	215.21	3	71.74	14.55
D	1268.65	3	422.88	85.80
SS error	251.37	51	4.93	
SS total	2402.57	63	38.14	

Table 4f: ANOVA for Cadmium

Factor	Sum of Square	Degree of freedom	Mean Sum of Square	F-Value
A	1734.69	3	578.23	256.35
B	260.27	3	86.76	38.46
C	411.30	3	137.10	60.78
D	373.59	3	124.53	55.21
SS error	115.03	51	2.26	1.00
SS total	2894.88	63	45.95	20.37

Figure 6a: Optimization of Factors for Turbidity using Taguchi Technique (Volume Ratio and Time)

Figure 6b: Optimization of Factors for Turbidity using Taguchi Technique (Spacing and Current)

Figure 7a: Optimization of Factors for Lead Concentration using Taguchi Technique (Volume Ratio and Time)

Figure 7b: Optimization of Factors for Lead Concentration using Taguchi Technique (Spacing and Current)

Figure 8a: Optimization of Factors for Cadmium Concentration using Taguchi Technique (Volume Ratio and Time)

Figure 8b: Optimization of Factors for Cadmium Concentration using Taguchi Technique (Spacing and Current)

CONCLUSION

It can be concluded that the turbidity of the water in Opa Dam is caused by mining activities within the catchment of the dam. The performance average using aluminium-aluminium electrode of turbidity, TDS, chloride, zinc, lead and cadmium were 43.934 %, 68.703 %, 68.389 %, 51.049 %, 21.797 %, 34.407 % and 29.460 % respectively, with lead having the least performance (21.797 %) and total dissolved solids having the highest performance (68.703 %). The selected factors (volume of water to electrolyte ratio, treatment duration, electrode spacing and applied current) were efficient in the removal of turbidity, TDS, zinc, lead and cadmiums. The volume of water to electrolyte ratio was not a significant factor on the removal of chloride from turbid water. The optimum values of each of the selected factors varies with the parameters to be removed while the general optimum values for the selected factors (volume of water to electrolyte ratio, treatment duration, electrode spacing and applied current) were; 1.70, 37 minutes, 1.25 cm and 1.75 A respectively.

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